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Predicting Electrical Changes in Skin Conductance Response Using Mobile Lens with a Custom Application

History

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Introduction

The initial and foremost thing to take into account is the bandwidth, for normal EDA it is set between 50-100 (μs), depending on the body texture and sensitivity to stimulus, and the videos are recorded at 25-35 frames per second depending on the shot and it is more than four times the minimum rate. The desired signal to be processed is the brightness of the skin and moisture content on the skin. Though it is not assured that all pixels in the images may contain brightness variation the processing pipeline stays computationally light. All the pixels can be combined into a single average brightness value per frame. The algorithm is implemented in real time. The entire process is computationally cheaper and gives both accurate and similar results to other standard models. Here, we present evidence that is scalable, quite

inexpensive, and non-invasive EDA and ST sensing that can be done through repurposing passive monitoring of Mobile camera lens tracking in real-time.

Other methods have used touchpads in PCs to measure the stress and relaxation of

participants (*Goel et al. (2020a); Sioni et al. (2014); Li (2022); Silva et al. (2021b); Dexheimer et al. (2017)*) and stress

has been known to have a profound impact on the cognitive and emotional well-being of users. Advances in some wearable technology enable effective and cognitive state measurements but they also have their drawbacks such as suffering from high attribution and low adoption and getting stable stress measurements from physiological metrics like heart rate and electrodermal activity (*Bhoja et al. (2020); Ahmadi et al. (2022); Liu and Du (2018); Rahma et al. (2022); Sun et al. (2012)*)).

Other

means of measurement are through camera light lenses on mobile phones that ensure both simultaneous and parallel processing and accuracy.

Abstract: *Different apps can read the heart rate with a smartphone camera from the index finger placed on it, without external pulsometers, but none can read an Electrodermal activity (EDA) from the fingertips, most of the procedure is simply to press the smartphone camera lens gently with the finger and within a few seconds the readings are shown on the integrated app of the physiological signal. The main of this paper is to use a signal and image processing pipeline to estimate the Electrodermal activity based on the concept of Heart rate evolution over time from a video sequence of a fingertip touching the camera lens. Error in signal acquisition for inner EDA on the lens and outer EDA on the lens was based on a third-order differential equation.*

Keywords: *EDA, Video sequence processing, Finger-tip on lens sensor, Light travel, Third-order differential equation, Cognitive analytics*

Previous laboratory studies have also shown that data from both interactions with everyday touchpad devices and lenses from computer mouse movements, keypad pressure, and smartphone touch that has key swipes or steering wheel are used in an unobtrusive and scalable way to detect physiological response that relay acute stress and relaxed mood. Some papers (Goel et al. (2020b); Silva et al. (2021a); Minguillon et al. (2018); Meena et al. (2017); Voulgaropoulou et al. (2023)), present pilot work that shows the feasibility of detecting acute stress from interactions with laptop computer trackpads.

Literature Review

There is also research that uses personal computing devices (PCDs) to deploy real-world responses to stress, and this number has increased by three million every year (Wang et al. (2023); Tsiourti et al. (2018); Fisher et al. (2005); Pisha et al. (2019); Wilcox (2015)). Personal laptops and tablets represent the largest and the fastest-growing devices among PCDs. Some laptop users prefer the trackpad over an external mouse for improving mobility and sensory tracking due to space limitations. Investigations on biomechanics and motor control for finger dynamics and tracking using a trackpad (MacRitchie and McPherson (2015); Goel et al. (2020c); Westerman (1999); Erol et al. (2007)) can lead to reliable detection of acute EDA and ST, especially for long term unobtrusive continuous monitoring. Details of the method proposed in this paper are discussed in the proceeding sections.

Figure 1: Finger tips on Mobile Camera lens.

Method

When the finger makes contact with the Mobile lens, the skin inside reflects the receptor skin surface from the outside, and its moisture content is measured. The skin

inside also indicates visible physical contact to light conversion to the optical system or mode, which is directed by the image sensor to a receiver channel in the form of the Android tablet that contains a dynamic motor control that performs extraction classified perception for visible predicted cognitive response detected and relayed back to the mobile. We were able to visualise the response readings (signal from the mobile while interacting). Five participants were recruited for the study to test their EDA and ST measures from the finger-tip contact to the mobile camera lens (Figure 2). Some of its dynamics are also explained in the introduction section. At the initial stage, the participants were asked to place their forefinger on the camera lens (Figure 1) and their EDA and ST were recorded continuously on a tablet offline. One of the input parameters is the amount of moisture content on the skin surface, which is equivalent to the EDA and measured in a continuous timestamp. The moisture content on the skin is given as in Equation 1.

$$MC_{skin} = \frac{w_{skin_{con}} - w_{Environment}}{w_{Environment}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where $WC_{skin_{con}}$ = moisture content expressed as a percentage due to reaction from the skin. $w_{skin_{con}}$ = weight in skin condition to task performance. $w_{Environment}$ = weight of skin to environmental constraint.

The predicted fingerprint, in this case, is equivalent to the moisture content of the skin due to task performance and as a result of the electrical changes of the skin due to reaction to perceived stimuli this is given as:

$$X_i = MC_{skin}(t)n. \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3x}{dy^3} &= a \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} + b \frac{dx}{dy} + c; \\ x &= \int_{i=1}^n 3 \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} - 2a \frac{dx}{dy} - b; \\ y &= ax + c \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where a, b, c are constants due to environmental constraints, x represents the rate of change of conduction with the lens through the moisture content MC_{skin} as an input matrix of the sensor output produced by the image detector, and this produces the resultant reaction y as a vector matrix, a cognitive response or reaction to stimuli on the skin surface.

The second stage is addressing the mechanism adopted in the concept of the touch lens of a Mobile phone (Samsung Android) as the electric conductor of signal from the skin to the lens surface, Figure 1 describes the concept while Figure 2 describes the mechanism and model representation. There are three kinds of structure for the module with resistive touch panels, these are (1) lens glass and (2) polycarbonate, and (3) light. This part of the scheme and a more common structure are also used for conductivity touch panels as a form of film/glass. The

Figure 2: A Simple processing pipeline to extract the EDA and ST over time from a video sequence of the fingertip skin conductance to light ray from a Mobile lens.

only significant difference between these two is the material at the bottom of the sensor and the accompanying support. The conductive touch sensors are made of glass as mentioned above, which are covered with electrically conductive and resistance layers (made of film coating) and covered with Indium-tin-oxide as a lens containing the light condenser, elastomer for finger contact with the lens and camera (Figure 1) that captures the image input from the lens. This also registers the moisture content of the skin surface and can be tracked continuously in short time intervals, the light conductive plate captures the image and its reflected in the marker displaced has the HOG features using image processing.

Result

The inference engine in the EDA analytical tool (Figure 4), is used to visualise and record the response reading from the lens from moisture content detected on the finger capture input image. The amount of moisture content is simulated with time using the third-order differential Equation 3. The initial signal contains noisy parameters due to some environmental factors such as background noise and distraction. The latency rate is based on the hand-clap signal that relays a stimulus onset. The Savitsky Golay filter based on a moving average is used to filter the signal for a clear reading. The tonic and phasic changes can be visual using the controls with embedded modules that compute the optimal and tonic response based on the minimum distance for each interval at a rate of forty-one minutes per second. The ST is simply the hotness or coldness of the fingertips at the initial detected offset and latency value at the start time.

Error in EDA measure was conducted for both inner and outer EDA signal on the lens, Figure 5 shows the aggregate of error in measurement to the EDA data, the mean and standard (SD) of the contact area under the finger are higher at the start point while the fingers were placed on the lens, and this seems to be performed under stress versus the relaxed mood (mean area: $p = 0.019$, effect size = 0.85; SD area: $P = 0.02$, effect size = 0.59). The result shows that a little touch contact on the lens can also be used to detect binary levels of EDA i.e. for skin with a lack of conductivity and low moisture content.

Figure 6 also shows the EDA for an outer signal on the lens and the mean and SD of the contact area for outer EDA from finger-tip contact to the lens are higher at the initial touchpoint was performed under stress and relaxed mood similar to the result above which is (mean area: $p = 0.019$, effect size= 0.87; SD area: $P = 0.03$, effect size = 0.69). The results show that subtle motion

Figure 3: Network architecture of touch lens for the finger to mobile less, image processed by the camera is sent has light conductive and relayed as marker displacement using HOG features.

Figure 4: The window interface showing the index page of the analytical tool for data visualisation and parameter detection.

on the touch lens can also be used to detect logical levels of stress mood whether it is present or not present at all.

Conclusion

The feasibility of this paper demonstrates the possibility of using soft-electrodermal a physiological analytical tool to detect the electrical changes of the skin using the mobile lens. The main aim of the paper is to use a signal and image processing pipeline to estimate the Electrodermal activity based on the concept of Heart rate evolution over time from a video sequence of a fingertip touching the camera lens. When the camera is covered by the fingertips, the naked eye sees only a static red frame but there exists a subtle variation caused by moisture content and blood flow under the skin, which can be recovered through video processing signal output. The modules used ambient light to travel through finger tissue and reach the camera sensor. The static red frame is captured and the fingerprint is recorded in a period of oscillation of moisture content based on a third-order differential equation and produces weak brightness variations that could be detectable to the naked eye and can be processed through signal dispensation. Most of the experimental

Figure 5: Error in time for inner EDA at lens point-based classified tonic and phasic represented by stress and relaxed mood.

Figure 6: Error measure on outer EDA with time at lens point with little marginal error.

study was done offline with a Samsung Android phone, data generated was copied to another PC for analysis and data visualisation the inference engine (control motor dynamics) is embedded in a custom analytical tool

for physiological response visualisation. Error in signal acquisition for inner EDA on the lens and outer EDA on the lens indicates the synchronous effect of response attributes for both the outer and inner EDA response at the lens point. The future perspective is to use the concept to develop a more authentic and visual response detection based on subtle vibration detected from inner lens contact and visualised through the analytical tool.

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References

Nima Ahmadi, Farzan Sasangohar, Tariq Nisar, Valerie Danesh, Ethan Larsen, Ineen Sultana, and Rita Bosetti. Quantifying occupational stress in intensive care unit nurses: An applied naturalistic study of correlations among stress, heart rate, electrodermal activity, and skin temperature. *Human Factors*, 64(1):159–172, 2022.

Ravi Bhoja, Oren T Guttman, Amanda A Fox, Emily Melikman, Matthew Kosemund, and Kevin J Gingrich. Psychophysiological stress indicators of heart rate variability and electrodermal activity with application in healthcare simulation research. *Simulation in Healthcare*, 15(1):39–45, 2020.

Judith W Dexheimer, Brad G Kurowski, Shilo H Anders, Nicole McClanahan, Shari L Wade, and Lynn Babcock. Usability evaluation of the smart application for youth with mtbi. *International journal of medical informatics*, 97:163–170, 2017.

Ali Erol, George Bebis, Mircea Nicolescu, Richard D Boyle, and Xander Twombly. Vision-based hand pose estimation: A review. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, 108(1-2):52–73, 2007.

Joseph A Fisher, Paolo Faraboschi, and Cliff Young. *Embedded computing: a VLIW approach to architecture, compilers and tools*. Elsevier, 2005.

Rahul Goel, Michael An, Hugo Alayrangues, Amirhossein Koneshloo, Emmanuel Thierry Lincoln, and Pablo Enrique Paredes. Stress tracker—detecting acute stress from a trackpad: Controlled study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(10):e22743, 2020a.

Rahul Goel, Michael An, Hugo Alayrangues, Amirhossein Koneshloo, Emmanuel Thierry Lincoln, and Pablo Enrique Paredes. Stress tracker—detecting acute stress from a trackpad: Controlled study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(10):e22743, 2020b.

Rahul Goel, Michael An, Hugo Alayrangues, Amirhossein Koneshloo, Emmanuel Thierry Lincoln, and Pablo Enrique Paredes. Stress tracker—detecting acute stress from a trackpad: Controlled study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(10):e22743, 2020c.

Zijin Li. *To VR or to PC?: Comparing Player Experience and Physiological Reaction in Superhot VR vs Superhot PC*. PhD thesis, Northeastern University, 2022.

Yun Liu and Siqing Du. Psychological stress level detection based on electrodermal activity. *Behavioural brain research*, 341:50–53, 2018.

Jennifer MacRitchie and Andrew P McPherson. Integrating optical finger motion tracking with surface touch events. *Frontiers in psychology*, 6:134939, 2015.

Yogesh Kumar Meena, Hubert Cecotti, KongFatt Wong-Lin, and Girijesh Prasad. A multimodal interface to resolve the midas-touch problem in gaze controlled wheelchair. In *2017 39th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, pages 905–908. IEEE, 2017.

Jesus Minguillon, Eduardo Perez, Miguel Angel Lopez-Gordo, Francisco Pelayo, and Maria Jose Sanchez-Carrion. Portable system for real-time detection of stress level. *Sensors*, 18(8):2504, 2018.

Louis Pisha, Julian Warchall, Tamara Zubatiy, Sean Hamilton, Ching-Hua Lee, Ganz Chockalingam, Patrick P Mercier, Rajesh Gupta, Bhaskar D Rao, and Harinath Garudadri. A wearable, extensible, open-source platform for hearing healthcare research. *IEEE Access*, 7:162083–162101, 2019.

Osmalina Nur Rahma, Alfian Pramudita Putra, Akif Rahmatillah, Yang Sa'ada Kamila Ariyansah Putri, Nuzula Dwi Fajriaty, Khusnul Ain, and Rifai Chai. Electrodermal activity for measuring cognitive and emotional stress level. *Journal of Medical Signals & Sensors*, 12(2):155–162, 2022.

Dennis R da C Silva, Zelun Wang, and Ricardo Gutierrez-Osuna. Towards participant-independent stress detection using instrumented peripherals. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 14(1):773–787, 2021a.

Dennis R da C Silva, Zelun Wang, and Ricardo Gutierrez-Osuna. Towards participant-independent stress detection using instrumented peripherals. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 14(1):773–787, 2021b.

Riccardo Sioni et al. Stress detection with physiological sensors for evaluating interactive systems and building relaxation training applications. 2014.

Feng-Tso Sun, Cynthia Kuo, Heng-Tze Cheng, Senaka Buthpitiya, Patricia Collins, and Martin Griss.

Activity-aware mental stress detection using physiological sensors. In *Mobile Computing, Applications, and Services: Second International ICST Conference, MobiCASE 2010, Santa Clara, CA, USA, October 25-28, 2010, Revised Selected Papers 2*, pages 282–301. Springer, 2012.

Christiana Tsiourti, Maher Ben Moussa, Joao Quintas, Ben Loke, Inge Jochem, Joana Albuquerque Lopes, and Dimitri Konstantas. A virtual assistive companion for older adults: design implications for a real-world application. In *Proceedings of SAI Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys) 2016: Volume 1*, pages 1014–1033. Springer, 2018.

Stella D Voulgaropoulou, Claudia Vingerhoets, Katya Brat-Matchett, Therese van Amelsvoort, and Dennis Hernaus. Perceived chronic stress and impulsivity are associated with reduced learning about the costs and benefits of actions. *Learning and Motivation*, 83:101896, 2023.

Lingzhe Wang, Daniel A Dalgo, Nicholas Mattise, Shengwei Zhu, and Jelena Srebric. Physiological responses and data-driven thermal comfort models with personal conditioning devices (pcd). *Building and Environment*, 236:110290, 2023.

Wayne Westerman. *Hand tracking, finger identification, and chordic manipulation on a multi-touch surface*. Citeseer, 1999.

Eric Scott Wilcox. *A Relay Prevention Technique for Near Field Communication*. PhD thesis, 2015.